

DISCURSIVE CONSTRUCTION OF IDENTITY IN DIGITAL COMMUNICATION

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola raqamli muloqot jarayonida shaxsiylik (identiklik) qanday diskursiv tarzda shakllanishini o'rganadi. Maqolada raqamli makonlar faqat dunyoning turli burchaklaridagi insonlar bilan muloqot qilish imkoniyati emas, balki shaxsni ifodalash maydoni ekani ta'kidlanadi. Unda til, belgilar va boshqa multimodal amaliyotlar orqali insonlar o'zlarini va boshqalarni qanday ta'riflashlari ko'rsatiladi. Tadqiqot shaxslarning onlayn muhitda o'z shaxsiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy identikliklarini namoyon etishining aniq usullarini yoritadi.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется, как идентичность формируется дискурсивно в процессе цифровой коммуникации. Автор утверждает, что цифровые пространства представляют собой не только возможность общения с людьми из разных частей мира, но и арену самовыражения, где язык, символы и другие мультимодальные практики способствуют тому, как люди определяют себя и других. Исследование подчеркивает конкретные способы, с помощью которых личности демонстрируют свои личные, социальные и культурные идентичности в онлайн-среде.

Abstract: This paper investigates how identity is discursively built during digital communication of people. It argues that digital spaces are not solely the opportunity to interact with different people from different parts of the world, but also demonstration of identity performance where language, symbols and other multimodal practices contribute to how people define themselves and others. This study highlights specific ways of individuals to show their personal, social, and cultural identities in online environments.

Keywords: Digital communication; discourse analysis; identity construction; multimodality; social media; code-switching; cultural identity; communities of practice.

Introduction

In the last two decades, digital communication has become one of the most important domains where people exchange ideas, construct, negotiate, and show identity. Platforms, including social media, online forums, messengers have granted individuals the opportunity to present themselves, change between identities and position themselves in relation to other users. Therefore, communication is no longer dominated by writing; diverse modes, such as visual, gesture, sound play equal roles (Kress, 2012). Discursive identity construction in online settings has been observed in 3 dimensions: personal, social and cultural identities.

Methodology

The study was based on qualitative and observational measure, focusing on naturally occurring digital discourse. Data was collected from social media interactions, such as posts, comments, stories, group chats, and online forums. Ethically, all the data was anonymized to protect identities of participants. Additionally, a teacher observed the texting of students in WhatsApp and Telegram groups, several LMS discussion chat boxes.

The method of analysis paid much attention to the following aspects:

Lexical choices- word choice and stylistic variation

Interactional patterns- how participants agree, disagree or negotiate

Multimodal elements- use of emojis, hashtags, gifs, stickers, or memes

Analysis

In the digital spaces, individuals mostly create their personal identity through profile features and linguistic choices when introducing themselves. For example, a user might describe himself or herself as a “traveler, dreamer, and coffee lover”. In the bio s/he might write quotes or proverbs, sayings that they like or define them. The use of humor, metaphors, or selected adjectives serve for self-presentation, allowing the speaker, writer to make a particular image of themselves on others.

Discourse analysis studies language as evidence of broader social phenomena, rather than only individual expression. For example, ancient scripts, letters did not only define personal views, but also societal norms and values of the time (Taylor, 2013). Nowadays, hashtags, memes, group discussions and polls can create affiliation with communities of practice. This is because they create a sense of belonging and shared identity, which are key features of communities of practice. Through these online interactions, people learn, share ideas, and build relationships. Additionally, shared slangs, in-group abbreviations can exclude outsiders by reinforcing solidarity among insiders.

In multilingual contexts, switching between languages can become a resource of constructing cultural identity. In a company employing Uzbek, Russian and English language speakers, a Telegram or WhatsApp group can show code and style switching depending on the speakers, communicators in the chat. The choice of greetings in first or foreign language, humor or cultural references signal affiliations again which go beyond the immediate interaction.

Findings

1. Identity is performed, not always possessed. Digital communication demonstrates how identity is flexible, and context-dependent.

2. Multimodality has expanded identity work. Emojis, GIFs, choice of video or text messages, images, and memes can go beyond written text to shape how users present themselves and how others interpret them. the ones who struggle to express themselves by texting has a chance to present with audio or video messages, by sending stickers or emojis.

3. Language choice is central. Code-switching, stylistic shifts, and lexical choices serve as resources for identity alignment or distancing.

4. Group belonging is discursively marked. Online communities are maintained through recurring discursive practices, insider language, and symbolic markers like hashtags, abbreviations.

Conclusion

As a meaning-making as part of social processes (Fairclough, 2012), discourse can show identity of humans, societies and cultures in state-of-the art mode of communication which include digital tools for interactions. The findings can easily show the huge role of discourse analysis in understanding contemporary way of communication. As digital platforms continue to develop, the ways in which identities are performed will also keep changing. Future research might explore specific genres of online discourse, such as activism, online learning, or professional networking, in order to further understand the connection between identity and digital discourse.

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